

UNPATH'D WATERS: Integrating Collections

Research Report: Work Package 1

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Julian Richards, Jamie Bradley,
Tim Evans, Kieron Niven, Émilie
Pagé-Perron, and Holly Wright

Table of Contents

Integrating Collections: Work Package 1	2
1.1 Acknowledgements	2
1.2 Aims and Objectives	2
1.3 The Resources	3
1.4 The Existing Digital Infrastructures	4
1.5 Ontologies and Data Structure	5
1.6 Data Mapping	6
1.7 Metadata Enhancement	7
1.8 The Unpath'd Waters Portal	7
1.9 Data Provision to External Portals	11
1.10 Challenges with the datasets	11
1.11 Updating the ADS Guide to Good Practice for Marine Survey.....	11
Bibliography.....	16

Integrating Collections: Work Package 1

Julian Richards, Jamie Bradley, Tim Evans, Kieron Niven, Émile Pagé-Perron and Holly Wright

Establishing a robust, secure and coherent base for the sample of all the digital collections that Unpath'd Waters was to explore was the responsibility of our Work Package 1 (Aggregation and Characterisation).

1.1 Acknowledgements

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1.2 Aims and Objectives

Led by the Archaeology Data Service but drawing on support from a wide range of the project Co-Is and Collaborating Organisations, the aim of WP1 was to investigate how to integrate the UK's marine collections, providing an exemplar for Towards a National Collection of the challenges of the aggregation of heterogeneous heritage data. The five subsidiary objectives were to:

- i. assess, aggregate and catalogue the digital components of the UK's marine national collections
- ii. assess the demands and capabilities of existing digital infrastructures
- iii. enhance this collection and deliver it to researchers and the public via existing and new human and machine-readable interfaces
- iv. develop appropriate data standards to achieve interoperability
- v. provide means of sustainable access routes and a primary data archive for UNPATH data outputs.

The first stage for WP1 was therefore to create an informal catalogue of the potential data sources that describe the UK's maritime heritage. Given the huge variety of sources, as well as their heterogeneous, disparate and fragmented nature, it was accepted from the outset that this was never going to be a comprehensive catalogue. As the resource is also dynamic as new discoveries are made all the time, it was also clear that it would be a snapshot in time, providing a demonstrator for TaNC, but that we could provide recommendations for how such catalogues might be maintained as live resources in the future.

During the proposal stage it was also agreed that the optimal approach would be to combine a large number of "thin" metadata records, providing national coverage, with a smaller number of much richer "thick" collections reflecting individual digital collections, thereby demonstrating both the breadth and depth of the

national collection. It was also considered important to reflect the fact that many research resources are not in digital form, but to show how digital records could provide an analogue-digital connector, pointing users to offline resources.

1.3 The Resources

After the assessment of available data, for the "thin" records it was decided to prioritise the aggregation of maritime data from the five national inventories maintained by the heritage agencies for England, Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, and the Isle of Man, all partners in the project, and giving full UK coverage. These are essentially sites and monuments inventories, sharing similar data structures, but with differences in data schema and vocabularies. In each case the agencies have responsibility for maintaining a national record; all make it available online via their own digital infrastructures and most use stable identifiers. In each case, therefore the slim metadata record harvested by Unpath'd Waters links to the primary record, and changes and updates to the core record do not affect the metadata link, so long as the link address is maintained. In some cases, we linked direct to the live record; in other cases, to a brokered record hosted by the ADS.

Although it was relatively easy to extract the shipwreck and aircraft loss records from the national records, one of the goals of Unpath'd Waters was to include maritime records found on land, including lighthouses, dock and shipyard structures, canal locks and maritime monuments. This could only be achieved by a relatively arbitrary choice of keywords which were used to extract additional records, resulting in a patchier coverage of land-based records.

In contrast to the authoritative national records provided by the state heritage agencies, we were also able to aggregate the very different national dataset, which was the outcome of the CITIZAN project, undertaken by MOLA. CITIZAN, the Coastal and InterTidal Zone Archaeological Network, was a community archaeology and citizen science project set up to create a written and photographic record of the coastal and intertidal zone. Messages in Bottles, created by the late Ed Cummings and maintained by the Nautical Archaeological Society, was a similar type of community-generated resource, in this case providing evocative details of messages recovered from bottles found on the seashore in the 19th Century, written by persons aboard distressed vessels, and recorded by Lloyd's of London and in the British Press. This collection presents significant difficulties (such as lack of locational data for the loss, authenticity), but has been added to the Unpath'd Waters Portal¹.

For the thicker "event" records referring to underwater archaeological fieldwork and research we used two categories of data managed by ADS. Firstly, we identified fieldwork reports referring to maritime interventions which had been logged in the national OASIS fieldwork recording system. Metadata for these was uploaded from the ADS Library, including DOI links to the full PDF reports curated by ADS. As a result of a contact made at the first TaNC conference we were able to include within the library an additional 240 reports of desk-based wrecks created by members of MADU (Malvern Archaeological Diving Unit) during Covid lockdown. These provide another example of the integration of a 'Citizen Science' dataset.

In addition, we included metadata links, again with DOIs, to complete ADS digital archives, each containing a rich range of marine survey and excavation data files. A second source of fieldwork data came from iMarDIS (The Integrated Marine Data and Information System), maintained by Bangor University. This contains

¹ <https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/search?creator=Jack%20Pink>

marine survey data, including multibeam bathymetric surveys undertaken by Bangor University (see companion Research Report for Work Package 3.2. For the wreck of the Mary Rose we created an additional ADS archive, including some 100 images of artefacts found in the wreck. We wanted to use this case study to show how data could be aggregated at item level, in this case individual objects recovered from the wreck, and searched alongside data for complete wrecks.

For the work on the Analogue-Digital Connector (see Research Report for WP3.1) we took a small set of records from Portsmouth University, reflecting their desk-based research on the wrecks in the area of the Needles, Isle of Wight, and including identifiers for paper documents and charts held by the UKHO and The National Archives.

A summary of the various resources used in UNPATH is as follows:

Sites and Monuments

- England – 50,680
- Scotland – 33,379
- Wales – 8,285
- Northern Ireland - 627
- Isle of Man – 1,916

Citizen Science

- CITIZAN – 3,875 records, with images
- Messages in Bottles – 384 records
- MADU – 240 reports

Fieldwork reports

- ADS – 300 grey literature reports

Fieldwork archives

- Underwater survey & excavation – ADS 94 records
- Multibeam survey – 358 records from Bangor
- Mary Rose archive – 100 artefacts with images

Analogue to Digital connectors

- Bangor & Portsmouth – >70 records

1.4 The Existing Digital Infrastructures

Before Unpath'd Waters there was no single means of interrogating the UK's maritime heritage. In common with the wider UK heritage record, the maritime record is split between the constituent nations, with independent infrastructures for England, Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, and the Isle of Man. This makes curatorial sense, but is an impediment to wider research, heritage management, and public interest, where

the UK coastal waters need to be viewed as a whole. The Marine Environmental Data and Information Network (MEDIN) portal² provides UK coverage for marine resources of all disciplines, but not at the level of individual wrecks. The Archaeology Data Service provides a UK wide archaeology catalogue, ArchSearch, but it is difficult to isolate maritime data in this interface. Data catalogued for Unpath'd Waters was also provided to both these infrastructures but neither provides an ideal UK wide interface for the project.

At proposal stage it was therefore agreed that Unpath'd Waters would build upon the digital infrastructure developed by the ARIADNE RI, which provides an international aggregation portal for archaeology and heritage. The ARIADNE portal and its underlying architecture had been developed with European research infrastructure funding over the previous decade, with two four-year projects: ARIADNE, and ARIADNEplus (Richards 2023)³. The portal sits on top of a Linked Open Data triplestore, and the ontology is based upon CIDOC CRM, so it should be extensible for other projects. The ADS decided to use Unpath'd Waters to test if they could create a version of the ARIADNE portal hardwired for UK maritime data. The metadata harvested for Unpath'd Waters was therefore loaded into the existing ARIADNE triple store, but the Unpath'd Waters Portal (see section 1.7 below) provides a hardwired view of a subset of the wider knowledge base. The approach demonstrates the principle that data (and metadata) can be stored once, but can be re-used many times, in interfaces which are tailored for different audiences. Since the data sits in a triple store it can also be directly queried and is available for human and machine interrogation via SPARQL queries.

1.5 Ontologies and Data Structure

The ARIADNE Ontology, AO for short, was developed at the start of the ARIADNEplus project for the purpose of integrating the archaeological data of the ARIADNE partners into a common information space. Building upon earlier projects, the CIDOC CRM, the standard ontology in the cultural heritage domain, was adopted as the conceptual backbone of the AO, providing a unified and coherent linguistic and axiomatic framework. Subsequently, the CRM has been specialised, under a specially devised namespace, to cater to the needs of the different subdomains covered by ARIADNE. The first of those specialisations was the AO-Cat, the part of AO dealing with the representation of the resources in the ARIADNE Catalogue. After testing the AO-Cat with Unpath'd Waters partners it was agreed that this covered the core metadata that would be needed to describe the digital resources that would be aggregated. The ontology is based around the attributes of What, When and Where, which underpin a powerful and intuitive search interface. Therefore, for Unpath'd Waters it was agreed to implement a further specialisation of the AO, defined as the UO-Cat. The only suggested addition required for the UO-Cat was that for maritime resources, to adequately describe 'Where', the property of Depth needed to be added to Easting and Northing. This was done, although in practice none of the datasets aggregated described depth in a consistent manner, so this attribute was not implemented in the portal interface.

The UNPATH knowledge base provides a collection-level representation of the resources shared by the project partners. However, while the distinction between collection level and item level may seem obvious, it can be applied in many ways, according to how we define what we consider to be items. This in turn depends on the specific research context and research question. For example, at the level of maritime landscape research, each wreck may be considered to be an item of observation, and the collection-level

² <https://medin.org.uk/using-medin-portal>

³ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

record refers to the site level record, whereas for an artefact-based study, individual objects may be the items of interest, and the collection-level record now refers to the database of artefacts, for example from the Mary Rose. But at each level the same attributes of What, When and Where can be applied.

1.6 Data Mapping

Having designated the UO-Cat as a shared ontology, interoperability between the partner resources was dependent upon mapping the data models of heterogeneous partner datasets to the UO-Cat. For this the X3ML Toolkit developed by FORTH was used. The X3ML Toolkit is a set of small, open source, microservices that follow the SYNERGY Reference Model of data provision and aggregation. It allowed us to define equivalences between the various attributes in partner-provided data with properties in the UO-Cat. However, to facilitate a useful cross-search it was also essential to achieve interoperability of the metadata used to describe the three main facets of 'Where', 'When' and 'What'. To support effective cross-search of metadata originating from many different partners requires some shared common understanding of the meaning of the metadata. The 'Where' and 'When' facets may be communicated using common data types and comparable values (e.g. spatial coordinates relative to a known location on the earth, date ranges relative to a known epoch). The 'What' (subject) aspect can be more difficult to define in a commonly understood and comparable format.

Despite the relatively advanced state of controlled vocabularies in the UK heritage sector, it became apparent that each of the agencies described maritime heritage in different ways, and at different levels of granularity. Rather than attempt to map every subject vocabulary to every other subject vocabulary it was agreed to map each vocabulary to a common spine (Binding et al. 2015). The Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) provides concepts and terms to describe cultural heritage concepts. The AAT is available as Linked Open Data, so each concept in the thesaurus has a unique identifier in the form of a URI (for example, <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300233041> is the identifier of the concept 'brigantine' – a specific type of vessel). Unpath'd Waters followed the approach tried and tested in ARIADNE by adopting the AAT as a central hub for scalable interconnection of local subject vocabularies. Mappings for most maritime terms had already been created by ADS for ARIADNE, and partners also provided additional mappings for their own local subject vocabulary (all terms used to describe subjects in their own metadata) to the AAT. It was noted, however, that at the fine level of vessel classification, the Getty AAT was not sufficiently granular to cover all categories of ship. In the longer term this could be resolved by requesting a formal extension to the Getty AAT. In the interim, the Unpath'd Waters Portal filters include a filter by "native subject" which can be used for more granular searches.

To deal with the spatial dimension, all spatial coordinates in Unpath'd Waters were expressed using the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84). This is a standard geographic coordinate system, comprising a global horizontal and vertical datum and a coordinate system used (particularly by GPS systems) to express global positioning on the surface of the Earth. This is essential in the maritime context, where the location of some sites is beyond the range of the respective national grid systems. Coordinates in local datasets sometimes required normalisation/transformation prior to aggregation in order to improve opportunities for cross searching the integrated datasets.

For the 'When' dimension we again followed the practice adopted in ARIADNE by asking partners to use the online Perio.Do⁴ period gazetteer service to define the 'From' and 'Until' absolute dates for cultural period terms. This gets around the problem that the date range of the Iron Age, for instance, is not the same in Scotland, Ireland, and England, allowing users to interrogate the knowledge base via the cultural period term, or via an absolute date range. An incidental impact of the project was that it led to a conversation between archaeologists of Northern Ireland and the Irish Republic, and an agreed set of Perio.Do definitions for the whole island of Ireland.

1.7 Metadata Enhancement

AI-based enhancement was used to enhance two of the datasets included within the Unpath'd Waters catalogue. The Welsh national record, Coflein, did not employ a detailed classification for vessel type, so most vessels were identified simply as "wreck". To provide interoperability with the records for England and Scotland it was therefore necessary to add more detailed subject terms for vessel types. The Southampton team employed an AI BERT model to extract vessel types from the free text descriptions in Coflein. Similarly, The Messages in a Bottle dataset simply comprised text reports, held as PDF files, providing transcriptions of the messages and information about where they were found. In this case Southampton extracted vessel names, dates and locations from the PDFs and, after further manual cleaning we were able to create a structured database which could be mapped to the UO-Cat and loaded to the triple store. In each case, however, it was important to distinguish the enhanced metadata from the primary record. We therefore added a gloss to each record noting that: "Subject keywords for maritime craft type recorded at time of loss have been enhanced by the University of Southampton using an AI BERT model as part of the Unpath'd Waters project. These do not form part of the official Coflein record".

1.8 The Unpath'd Waters Portal

As noted above, the Unpath'd Waters portal⁵ provides one view into the data held in the RDF triple store which forms the Knowledge Base used by the project. The triple store is currently managed by CNR ISTI in Pisa, and is held in an open-source version of Graph DB. As of August 2024, the triple store comprises 491,695,356 statements, or triples.

Data can be loaded to the triple store by different methods, but the majority of the Unpath'd Waters data was loaded as pre-prepared XML files and then enriched with Getty AAT terms during aggregation. However, the architecture also supports the use of APIs to load data to the triple store and automated harvesting using OAI-PMH. This can be set to harvest at regular intervals (e.g. daily, weekly, monthly) and would allow the portal to maintain an up-to-date window into the UK's maritime record.

⁴ <https://perio.do/en/>

⁵ <https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/>

Figure 1: The workflow to upload data to the Graph DB triple store, including enrichment stages

Various user-friendly interfaces can be built on top of the triple store. The current version of the ARIADNE portal uses Open Search indices to facilitate searching, browsing, and filtering records, according to the What, When, and Where parameters, but also allowing filtering by Publisher and Contributor, as well as Resource Type, a high-level subject classification. For the Unpath'd Waters portal we used geographical location and Resource Type to restrict searching to UK data, and Maritime records.

Figure 2: The Unpath'd Waters portal landing page

Spatial searching is enabled by a map-based interface. This displays the density of records in the selected view as a heat map. As the user zooms in further then individual records appear and can be selected.

Figure 3: The advanced spatial search interface, showing the heat map for UK maritime records

The results page displays all records which correspond to the selected filters and allows users to identify specific record of interest.

A full user guide to all the features of the portal is available⁶.

At the conclusion of the Unpath'd Waters project, the Portal provides access to over 100,000 digital resources, with complete UK coverage, and reflecting the full range of digital data (Table 1).

⁶ <https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/guide>

The screenshot shows the UNPATH'D WATERS Portal interface. On the left, there are search filters for 'Where' (a map of Europe) and 'When' (a line graph showing the number of resources over time). The main content area displays search results for 'The Hazardous Project', 'On the Importance of Shipwrecks', 'Charlestown Shipwreck and Heritage Centre', and 'Artefacts from the Sea'. Each result includes a description, resource type, publisher, and original subject.

Figure 4: The Portal results page, showing the Where and When search boxes on the lefthand side

Number of records	Provider	Dataset
National Inventories		
50,680	Historic England	AMIE dataset which forms the basis of Mariner
33,379	Historic Environment Scotland	Canmore
8,285	Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales	Coflein
627	Department for Communities, Northern Ireland	Northern Ireland Wrecks Database
1,916	Manx National Heritage	Isle of Man HER
Fieldwork		
540	Archaeology Data Service	Library of Fieldwork Reports, including 240 reports from MADU
94	Archaeology Data Service	ADS archives
359	Bangor University	iMarDIS
100	Mary Rose Trust	Artefact sample

Table 1: Resources aggregated via Unpath'd Waters

1.9 Data Provision to External Portals

Since the Unpath'd Waters portal was built on top of the Graph DB triple store managed by the ARIADNE RI, this has the bonus that data provided by partners automatically appears in the ARIADNE portal at the same time as it appears in the Unpath'd Waters portal. In this context it is cross-searchable with some four million heritage resources from some 40 countries and provides a showcase for the UK's marine heritage for an international audience.

Metadata was also supplied for the MEDIN portal for those datasets not already harvested from the MEDIN, including for CITIZAN and Messages in Bottles. For their audience, MEDIN chose to take single collection records for the national inventories, rather than individual site records, underlining that for a national collection different views into the data are needed for different audiences. This link to MEDIN exposed the Unpath'd Waters datasets to audiences beyond the heritage sector and enabled them to feed onto the digital infrastructure of the UN Ocean Decade.

1.10 Challenges with the datasets

A selection bias was identified within the Unpath'd Waters Portal during testing. The sample consisted of records relating to England sourced from the ADS, Historic England, the CITIZAN project and various other organisations; the majority of the Scottish records were contributed by HES. It appears that the Scottish records were a subset of the national database, CANMORE, and not all coastal and maritime records were included. This is apparent as the maritime data published for Scotland mainly relates to vessels of some sort, whereas a much broader definition of 'maritime' was applied in other nations. As the portal was designed to retrieve records relating to a variety of maritime site types, the inclusion of a subset of Scotland's coastal and maritime records meant that the results of any search are skewed, potentially leading to an erroneous belief that Scottish maritime heritage is markedly different from that in other nations. For example, a search on the term 'fish trap' revealed 294 records in England and Wales, but just 4 from Scotland, (a CANMORE search reveals 532 results). A search on key words 'pier' or 'harbour' appeared to give a more promising distribution of sites in Scotland, but drilling down into the records revealed that the majority of sites were again wrecks or hulks, with these key words appearing in the name of the location. In order to prevent a similar bias in any future iteration of the portal, the records available to the search engine should be based on proximity to the coast edge, rather than a predetermined subset.

1.11 Updating the ADS Guide to Good Practice for Marine Survey

Deanna Groom, Mike Roberts, Tim Evans, Kieron Niven, and Julian Richards)

One of the by-products of the work on aggregation of collections for Unpath'd Waters has been an updated edition of the ADS Guide to Good Practice (G2GP) for Marine Survey⁷. The original guide was written some 10 years ago, and key concerns related to developments in survey instrumentation, software, and file

⁷ <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/help-guidance/guides-to-good-practice/data-collection-and-fieldwork/marine-survey/introduction/marine-remote-sensing-in-archaeology/>

formats. In addition, there was a need to include more cross-references to standards produced by the Marine Environmental Data and Information Network (MEDIN). The project comprised the following stages:

- i. Bibliographic search;
- ii. Review of repositories and archive provision;
- iii. Review of project datasets already archived;
- iv. Review of the archiving guidance for the repositories making up the MEDIN Data Archiving Centre (DAC) network;
- v. Structured interviews with marine survey commissioners, archive repositories, archaeological contractors, and university staff known to be active in marine survey.

1.11.1 Bibliographic Search

The bibliographic search compiled a list of 205 published articles, reports, and guidance notes primarily from the past 10 years. Information about processing software (e.g. CARIS, SonarWhiz, Quinsy, Geosuite, Kingdom, etc) and the file formats used (e.g. .xtf, .txt, .sgy) was also compiled, to inform the file formats list in the updated G2GP. The search identified a broader range of survey techniques than had previously been included, particularly oceanographic data loggers gathering information about environmental parameters relating to preservation state and photogrammetry. The latter has now largely replaced traditional diver techniques, such as measured tape survey.

1.11.2 Defining the Archiving Network

Information about commissioners of marine surveys, data repositories, and producers of archaeological marine survey datasets, was also collated:

- Commissioners of Surveys– Historic England, Historic Environment Scotland, Cadw, and Department of Communities Northern Ireland, Marine and Coastguard Agency; Ministry of Defence, and Port Authorities;
- Portals – MEDIN, Marine Data Exchange, Admiralty Marine Data Portal, IMARDIS (Bangor University), Channel Coastal Observatory, Welsh Coastal Monitoring Centre, Northern Ireland Coastal Monitoring Centre;
- Archives – Historic Environment Scotland, Archaeology Data Service, Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historic Monuments of Wales; British Geological Survey; United Kingdom Hydrographic Office; British Marine Biological Association; British Oceanographic Data Centre;
- Producers – Universities (Bangor, Southampton, St Andrews, Ulster) and contract units (Maritime Archaeology Trust, Wessex Archaeology, MSDS, Cotswold Archaeology, Cornwall and Isles of Scilly Maritime Archaeology Society, Nautical Archaeology Society).

1.11.3 Structuring the Updated G2GP

The new guide has been structured with the full range of marine archaeological survey techniques producing digital data, namely:

Surface to seabed:

- Imagery – digital photographs and video;
- Photomosaics and photogrammetry;
- Bathymetric LiDAR;
- Underwater laser scanners;
- Side-scan sonar;
- Single and multi-beam echosounders;
- Oceanographic data loggers.

Imaging sediment layers and geophysical anomalies:

- Magnetometer;
- Pinger and Chirps;
- Boomer and Sparker;
- Parametric (non-linear) Sub-bottom Echosounder.

The section on file formats was organised to reflect the transformations which data passes through - from acquisition to final products. The tables show the different file formats that may characterise each stage. The updated G2GP details the full range of potential survey techniques, whereas the original deals primarily with marine geophysical data. It also presents a table of preferred file formats through the transformations of the different processing stages rather than just a single table of preferred archive formats.

1.11.4 Identifying Case Studies

Archaeological archives holdings were visited to identify projects which could be used as case studies for each survey technique. The identification of projects where survey data was archived with non-heritage MEDIN DAC institutions was a particular priority. Two good case studies were identified:

- The London Gateway project was found to be a complex project with marine survey datasets archived with the UKHO (UK Hydrographic Office) and British Geological Survey, and artefacts and hard copy archives with the Southend Museum service. The project reports are archived with the ADS⁸.
- The University of Southampton's survey of the Pudding Pan wreck in the Thames Estuary. The multibeam echosounder data is archived with the UKHO, with the reports archived with ADS.

⁸ <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archives/view/wessexar1-397949/index.cfm>

Sample data to help illustrate the guide was also taken from Bangor University's IMARDIS holdings (e.g. multibeam, oceanographic data loggers) and from British Geological Survey (e.g. magnetometer and sidescan) to show alongside the finished digital products.

1.11.5 Interviews

Twenty-two online interviews were conducted to further inform the new G2GP, and these also informed the recommendations which appear in the discussion section below.

1.11.6 Discussion

The process of updating the G2GP has highlighted several issues for future discussion:

- Heritage bodies and archives accept that some forms of marine survey data (MBS, SSS, SBP (Sub Bottom Profiler), Magnetometer, environmental data) will be archived with external bodies – that is the 'total archive' will be split across institutions. This approach requires sign up and agreement from all the devolved government heritage bodies and national heritage archive services.
- Whilst the survey instruments described in the revised G2GP can output in ASCII formats suitable for long term archiving, it remains true that specialist software is needed to view that data as 2D or 3D models. Consideration might be given to a project working with the survey software developers (e.g. Sonardyne, Chesapeake Technology, QPS) to raise awareness of heritage archiving issues and to develop free viewers for use by heritage archive staff to check data, for reading rooms access to data, and to embed in NMR online access to records (e.g. Fledermaus Viewer Fledermaus - QPS , Caris Easy View Easy View | Teledyne Geospatial (teledynecaris.com)). This would overcome the barrier of having to sign-up to expensive, ongoing, specialist software licences.
- The question of ADS archiving costs came up several times in relation to being a barrier for some depositors (e.g. costs of archiving are too large a portion of whole grant being given to undertake work; it is hard to estimate the costs of archiving in advance for the grant application). In comparison, there are no costs involved for archiving with the RCAHMW or HES. Of the other MEDIN DACs, BGS have modest charges, whilst the UKHO, BODC (British Oceanographic Data Centre) and Marine Biological Association are also free. This disparity needs to be addressed to reduce this barrier to archiving.
- The Coastal Monitoring Centres of England, Wales and Northern Ireland have not been contacted or their data holding fully explored as part of this project. The archiving of bathymetric LiDAR datasets is likely to be within their remit.
- Guidelines for acceptable file formats for long term archiving vary in their availability across the MEDIN DAC network. It would be extremely helpful to depositors if harmonisation could be achieved.
- The preference for the use of MEDIN metadata was expressed by various participants, hence there may be a requirement for a review of heritage archives metadata to ensure that their metadata requirements are harmonised (e.g. MEDIN requires depth to seabed field to be completed).

- Archaeological guidance is presently missing from the available MEDIN guidance pages⁹. Hence consideration might be given to using a version of the updated G2GP for that purpose.
- Participants referred to the inability of finding data on the portals – for example, often having to rely on the fact that they know that a contractor has undertaken a piece of work. A small project might be developed to look at the way that potential users wish to search for data in line with the FAIR principles.
- If a preference for only archiving raw data and final data products, a standard may have to be defined to improve metadata descriptions of the intermediate processing steps, so that re-users can fully understand how the data has been transformed and to provide insights into how data might be reprocessed to create new interpretations.
- MSDS have been commissioned to update Historic England’s Guidance Note ‘Marine Geophysics Data Acquisition, Processing and Interpretation’, which is in draft form with Historic England for review. Consideration should be given to reviewing the updated ADS G2GP’s alongside this new Guidance Note to ensure that there are no contradictions in policy.
- With regard to datasets produced in development control scenarios, there is a perception that the Data Clauses in Development Consent Orders ensure that reports and data generated from mitigation works are sent to the Marine Data Exchange for archiving, However, the Crown Estate’s recently revised guidance for Written Schemes of Investigation¹⁰ places the National Monuments Records of each country as the appropriate place. Hence there is a need for a review of a wider range of documents relating to best practice in offshore development control. This is needed to ensure consistency of message for what to archive and where. Participants have suggested that there is a need to keep talking about these ‘grey areas’ as they continue to cause uncertainty and frustration.
- Many interviewees favoured the provision of a single deposition portal, with the separation of datasets for archiving at the different MEDIN DAC institutions happening in the ‘background’ without further interaction needed by depositors. This was expressed alongside the wish for new guidance which could be widely promoted and become a single point of reference for everyone.
- There is a perception that there is still a legacy of unarchived data where a more proactive approach to chasing up and setting deadlines when archives must be deposited by commissioners of projects would be beneficial.

⁹ <https://medin.org.uk/data-standards/medin-data-guidelines>

¹⁰ <https://www.thecrownestate.co.uk/media/3917/guide-to-archaeological-requirements-for-offshore-wind.pdf>

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